

Seasonal clocks in the UK: back to the core issue

José María Martín-Olalla

Universidad de Sevilla
Facultad de Física,
Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada,
ES41012 Sevilla,
Spain*

Jorge Mira

Universidade de Santiago de Compostela
Facultade de Física,
Departamento de Física Aplicada and iMATUS,
ES15782 Santiago de Compostela,
Spain†

(Submitted: 1 April 2025)(Rejected: 28 April 2025)(Posted: 28 April 2025)

We present a response to the rebuttal by Crawford et al., addressing the fundamental issue at the heart of Daylight Saving Time regulations.

```
File: main.tex
Encoding: utf8
Words in text: 982
Words in headers: 14
Words outside text (captions, etc.): 64
Number of headers: 3
Number of floats/tables/figures: 0
Number of math inlines: 0
Number of math displayed: 0
Subcounts:
text+headers+captions (#headers/#floats/#inlines/#displayed)
919+11+64 (2/0/0/0) _top_
63+3+0 (1/0/0/0) Section: Manuscript time line
```

Keywords: DST; summer time; society; latitude; sleep deprivation; spring transition; Europe; America; season; motor vehicle accidents; myocardial infarction

We acknowledge Crawford et al.’s(Crawford *et al.*, 2025b) response to our response(Martín-Olalla and Mira, 2025b) to a British Sleep Society’s position statement on summertime regulations(Crawford *et al.*, 2025a). We love to think these exchanges help sharpen the arguments and clarify the issues at stakes in this topic, where science, society and politics meet.

At the time we wrote our Letter we were committed to the publishing of a position paper that reviewed the rationale behind seasonal clocks, and the modern criticism to this practice(Martín-Olalla and Mira, 2025a). In the writing of this study and during the review process—which is publicly available—we thoroughly discussed the issues that were addressed in our exchanges with sleep societies, including (i) the meaningful evidence of a century without responsive action to seasonal clocks—which

Crawford *et al.* (2025b) disregard (see their points 1 and 4)—; (ii) the impact of artificial light (point 2); (iii) transition dates (point 2);¹ and (iv) the interplay between clock regulations and personal preferences (point 2): current regulations also allow people to go contrarian, and demand later start times to enjoy summer mornings, but this demand is seldom observed, see (i).

We want to highlight a very interesting point in the response by Crawford *et al.* (2025b): in point 3 it is noted that should seasonal clocks be not enforced, then people could eventually wake up earlier and without the help of an alarm clock during the summer months. With no early

¹ A minor point is noted: the breakdown of a year in seasons is a human convention for practical purposes. Here there are two contrasted seasons: light (summer) and dark (winter). They are marked by the photoperiod being/not being larger than the equinoctial day (twelve hours). They correspond to the sun traveling/not traveling observer’s hemisphere. They match to spring-summer and autumn-winter usual seasons.

* olalla@us.es

† jorge.mira@usc.es

preset schedules they would remain in a stand-by until the (winter) start times arrive. After this decade-long discussion, we came back to the late 19th century, early 20th century core issue: the “waste” of daylight that gave birth to the “saving” of daylight so that “a long period of daylight leisure would be made available in the evening for (...) any (...) outdoor pursuit desired” (Hudson, 1898; Willet, 1907) To us, addressing this core issue is fairer and more honest, compared with previous calls that associate seasonal clocks with artificial settings, translocations of people, people living with another place’s sun, all sort of malides, and eventually with the claim that “this is a policy that literally kills people”, see Joanna Fong-Isariyawongse in Jacobs (2025).

Either ideas —the stand-by period and the rising without an alarm clock— points to the same fact: a change in behavioral patterns when winter and summer activity are compared. Seasonal clocks also bring a change in behavioral pattern, in that case and all else equal, the phase of human activity, with the illusion and simplification that a routine is, apparently, kept year round.

We do not ponder which solution is best from a healthy perspective or from the point of view of economics. We are telling that since 1916 the UK embraced the seemingly awkward proposal designed by Hudson (1898). It was never a question of increasing the daylight, but a question of when human activity should be placed in summer and, indirectly, in winter. People committed to the rule of thumb “duty first, before pleasure” instead of “a bit of pleasure, then duty, then more pleasure”. We observe that without seasonal clocks, people often shifted to earlier preset schedules, effectively reducing the “waste” of daylight in summer, *and* increasing the use of the dark hours of the winter dawn. (Martín-Olalla, 2018, 2022) Either way the wasting daylight was reduced in Europe. Therefore, we are noting that this stand-by period might have been abhorred in some societies. The very existence and sustainability of seasonal clocks *without responsive actions against* is evidence of the dislike.

We end with a personal anecdote. One of us, JMM-O, was told by a colleague: “I rather prefer permanent winter time”. To which JMM-O responded: “I am fine with that; look, you come here on bike, what are you going to do when in June or July the sun rose one hour earlier than you are used to, and you got involved in a hot morning with a high sun.” The response was: “that will be easy, I would come here earlier”. To which JMM-O looked surprised and got a follow-up: “oh I see, that’s what we get with the spring-forward change”.

The anecdote illustrates that clock regulations do not play against human physiology. But we will refine the argument. It is possible that that person may not necessarily choose a one-hour, biannual change in their daily routine. It is also possible that the end of March and the end of October [Europe’s current transition dates] would not be their transition dates of choice —we support a re-

setting of transition dates, specially autumn date—. For the better and for the worse this ends up in a social issue. Societies and individuals within a society can find outcomes when an issue of this kind is addressed in a synchronized way: children and parents, teachers and pupils, commuters and passengers, dealers and customers —all of them operating under preset, social schedules— stay in sync.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

FUNDING STATEMENT

This work was not funded.

REFERENCES

- Crawford, Megan R, Eva C. Winnebeck, Malcolm von Schantz, Maria Gardani, Michelle A. Miller, Victoria Revell, Alanna Hare, Caroline L. Horton, Simon Durrant, and Joerg Steier (2025a), “The british sleep society position statement on daylight saving time in the uk,” *Journal of Sleep Research* **34**, e14352.
- Crawford, Megan R, Eva C Winnebeck, Malcom von Schantz, Maria Gardani, Michelle A Miller, Victoria Revell, Alanna Hare, Caroline L Horton, Simon Durrant, and Joerg Steier (2025b), “Response to martin-olalla and mira’s letter to the editor ‘seasonal daylight saving time in uk: A long-standing, successful record with few reasons to alter’,” *Journal of Sleep Research* , e70022.
- Hudson, George Vernon (1898), “On seasonal time,” *Transactions and Proceedings of the New Zealand Royal Society* **31**, 577–598.
- Jacobs, Phie (2025), “Does daylight saving time make sense? scientists debate pros and cons,” AAAS Articles DO Group 10.1126/science.z0vspqy.
- Martín-Olalla, José María (2018), “Latitudinal trends in human primary activities: characterizing the winter day as a synchronizer,” *Scientific Reports* **8**, 5350.
- Martín-Olalla, José María (2022), “A chronobiological evaluation of the risks of canceling daylight saving time,” *Chronobiology International* **39**, 1–4.
- Martín-Olalla, José María, and Jorge Mira (2025a), “Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal of seasonal daylight saving time,” *The Royal Society Open Science* **12**, 240727.
- Martín-Olalla, José María, and Jorge Mira (2025b), “Seasonal daylight saving time in uk: a long-standing, successful record with few reasons to alter,” *Journal of Sleep Research* **34**, e14420.
- Willet, William (1907), *The waste of daylight*.

MANUSCRIPT TIME LINE

We learned of the response letter to our response letter after on 27 March 2025 the manuscript was added to the *Web of Science* database and the corresponding citing

alert was sent by email.

We sent the manuscript on 1 April 2025, and we got the response from the Editor on 28 April 2025. We understand that extended back-and-forth exchanges are often unwelcome.